

Valuation of the Effect of Herbicides on the Honey Bee *Apis mellifera* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Hymenoptera: Apidae) in Middle Iraq

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Abstract:

The study was conducted between February and April 2022 with the aim of knowing the effect of agricultural activities on the condition of the honey bee population in middle Iraq 30%, 17% and 11%, respectively. A survey of a set of data on traditional beekeepers, honey sellers and farmers were conducted. The survey was conducted in three selected areas of middle Iraq, namely Muqdadiyah, Dujail and Rashidiya, due to the prosperous of the beekeeping profession there. The methods of descriptive frequencies and chi-square (χ^2) were used in the statistical analysis of the obtained data. The percentage of beekeepers in the study area was

100% male, 64% of them were in the age group 60-82 years, 50% of them had primary education and had a number of beehives, 32% and 28% of them had secondary and university education, and the highest percentage of participants in beekeeping for those aged 38-26 years, it amounted to 50%, while the lowest percentage was for those over 45 years old, which was 4%. The population groups of honey bees ranged between a decrease and a moderate, high and slight increase due to death or migration or both reasons, in addition to the improper use of herbicides, the removal of trees and palm groves, pollution of river water and burning of the herbaceous areas at a certain rate for each reason amounting to 47%, 34%, 19%, 42%, 30%, 17% and 11% respectively. Therefore, pesticides and herbicides should not be used during the flowering period of plants. Chemical pesticides should be replaced with biological pesticides to reduce the toxicity of chemicals on insect appendages.

Keywords: *Apis mellifera*, bush burning, insect control, Apidae, honey bee.

Introduction

Honey bees are social insects that depend exclusively on flowering plants and act as a carrier of pollen from one flower to another (Mustafa et al, 2015). The relationship between flowering plants and bees has great economic importance, as it generates material revenues of more than 200 billion dollars annually in the form of food products, in addition to the successful reproduction of more than 85% of flowering plants (Oluwaseun 2009). This type of

insect can be considered an important part of the ecosystems, as it pollinates one third of the food consumed by humans, increases the biodiversity of different types of plants, and maintains them by regulating genetic diversity within many plant groups, and increases fruit production and thus supports plants and animals at every level of the food chain (Batra 1995). Although *Apis mellifera* L. is distributed in most countries of the world, Africa is its original habitat and its common habitat is Nigeria (Oluwaseun 2009).

In recent years, there has been an increase in the use of chemicals to clear and firing forests for agriculture, food and housing needs as a result of the increasing population. These activities can lead to the pollution of water bodies and flower nectar and the loss of many plant species, which in turn may affect the population groups of honey bees (Mohamed et al. 2015; Traynor et al. 2021). Because this species of beneficial insect is an important economic and vital resource, it requires protection and preservation in the meaning of biodiversity in different regions (Nnamonu and Onekutu, 2015; Kaya et al., 2023). Without the pollination process carried out by honey bees, the production of food crops would decrease by about a third. In addition to the impact on some fruit and vegetable crops and fodder used in raising livestock for meat and dairy production through the decrease in insect pollinators (Tirado et al., 2013). Residues of herbicides used can be found in plant pollen and nectar and can be toxic to honey bees because

they feed on them (Blacquiere, 2012). The main objective of this study was to evaluate the acute oral and contact toxic effects of some herbicides on adult honey bee workers (*A. mellifera* L.).

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The study was conducted in three areas in central Iraq, namely Muqdadiah, Dujail and Rashidiyah, according to the recorded coordinates (33° 53' 01.39 N, 44° 50' 54.42" E), bordered to the north by the governorates of Sulaymaniyah and Kirkuk, to the south by the governorates of Wasit and Babil, to the east by Iran and to the west by Anbar Governorate (Figure 1 and 2). The reason for choosing this area to conduct the research is the widespread prevalence of the profession of beekeeping there.

Figure 1. Map of Iraq

Figure 2. A Map of Middle Iraq Showing the Sample Collection Areas

Data Collection

The study was conducted from February to April 2022, and data were obtained from traditional beekeepers, honey sellers, and farmers, and included socio-demographic information related

to the agricultural activities of the population and their impact on the honey bee population.

Data Analysis

The data were statistically analyzed using the descriptive frequency method, which includes

the use of percentages and bar graphs to display the data obtained. The chi square was also used to determine the relationship between the agricultural activities carried out by the population and the status of honey bees in the study area (Angela et al., 2019).

Results

Demography of the Respondents

Table (1) shows that the majority of beekeepers in the area where the study was conducted, who numbered 75, were males aged between 60-82 years, as their percentage was found to be 64%, while the percentage of those aged between 45-60 years was 12%. The percentage of those under 45 years of age was found to be 24%. The table also shows that the percentages of beekeepers who have primary, secondary and university education are 50%, 32% and 28% respectively. It was found that the highest percentage of people participating in beekeeping was for those aged between 26 and 38 years, reaching 50%, while the lowest percentage was for those over 45 years, equal to 4%. The results also show that the percentage of beekeepers who own 36-50 hives is 40% and the percentage of those who own 92 hives is only 10% (Table 1). Knowing this percentage is of great importance in designing any program to protect bee colonies from the risks of herbicides (Tijani et al., 2011).

Table 1. Demographic Data of Beekeepers in the Study Area

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	75	100.0
	Female	0	0.0
Age	60 - 82	48	64.0
	45 - 60	9	12.0
	> 45	18	24.0
Educational qualification	Primary	38	50.0
	Secondary	24	32.0
	Tertiary	21	28.0
Beekeeping period (years)	26 - 38	9	50.0
	≤ 45	2	40.0
Number of hives owned	36 - 50	30	40.0
	92	8	10.0

Demographic Status of Honey Bee Population

95% of the beekeepers surveyed believed that the number of honey bees had declined significantly, while 5% believed that there had been an increase in the population of honey bees (Table 2). 47% of them noted that the reason for the decline was some deaths, while 34% of them confirmed that the main reason was the migration of large numbers of bees and 19% were of the opinion that the decline in the population of honey bees was a result of both factors (Table 2). The possible causes of the decline in the honey bee population in central Iraq are due to the improper use of herbicides (42%), the removal of trees and palm groves (30%), as well as the pollution of river water (17%) and the burning of bushes (11%) (Table 2). Many international studies have been conducted in this regard, including the study conducted by Dauda et al., (2019) on the impact of some agricultural activities carried out by farmers, including the use of herbicides, on the status of the honey bee *Apis mellifera* L. population in Katsina State, Nigeria. The researchers concluded through a preliminary questionnaire containing information related to the study distributed to a large number of beekeepers in the state and through statistical analysis of that information that the excessive use of pesticides, deforestation and burning of the bush had a significant impact on the numbers of honey bee populations by increasing the death rate and migration of large numbers of them. Stoner (2016) also studied the risk assessment of various pesticides currently used on honey bees (*Apis mellifera*) and bumblebees (*Bombus* spp.). The researcher confirmed that the results of that study showed sub-lethal effects of imidacloprid at the bumblebee colony level through its effect on feed and food consumption, and thus on the growth and reproduction of bee groups within a single colony and using lower concentrations than in honeybee colonies. The researcher found in that study that the lack of full effects of neonicotinoids on bumblebees is due to the difference in their life cycle from that of honeybees, in addition to the fact that they live

in colonies for a few months each year. Only sublethal effects of systemic insecticides at the population level affect the entire life cycle of honey bees, but only a portion of the annual life cycle of bumblebees (Straube et al., 2015). Different neonicotinoids have different effects on bumblebees at the neuronal level, and on forager bee feeding behavior at the individual and colony levels (Kessler et al., 2015; Moffat et al., 2016). Johanna et al. (2017) reported that pesticides have future environmental impacts on plants pollinated by bumblebees, and that interactions between pesticide molecules and other stressors have significant effects on individuals within the colony, such as the queen and other colony members. Other studies in this

field include what Aleksandra et al. (2021) did when studying the effect of pesticides and microbiological pollutants on the health of *Apis mellifera* bees. In that study, the researchers found that there was a significant decrease in the number of colonies of this species due to pesticides, as they found that they cause serious damage to the nervous system of bees and permanently weaken the immune system, making them vulnerable to other factors. Some pesticides that negatively affect bees, for example, neonicotinoids, coumaphos and chlorpyrifos, can cause various diseases of bees, which impair the health of the colony and often lead to its extinction (Yan Ping and Reinhold, 2007; Straub et al., 2015).

Table 2. Numbers of Honey Bees in Three Areas of Central Iraq and Their Possible Causes

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Population status of honey bees	Decreased	71	95.0
	Increased	4	5.0
	Moderate increase	46	61.0
	High increase	17	22.0
	Slight decrease	10, 3	13.0, 4.0
How the decrease occurred	By death	35	47.0
	By migration	25	34.0
	By both death and migration	15	19.0
	Improper use of herbicides	31	42.0
	Removal of trees and orchards	22	30.0
	River water pollution	13	17.0
	Burning bush	8	11.0

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the critical impact of agricultural practices, particularly the use of herbicides, on the honey bee population in middle Iraq. The findings reveal a significant decline in honey bee numbers, with 95% of surveyed beekeepers acknowledging this trend. The primary factors contributing to this decline include the improper use of herbicides (42%), deforestation (30%), pollution of river water (17%), and the burning of bushes (11%).

The research underscores the detrimental effects of herbicides not only on individual bees but also on the overall health of bee colonies. The study indicates that the excessive use of pesticides and herbicides leads to increased mortality rates and migration of bees, further exacerbating the

decline in populations. Additionally, the timing of herbicide application, especially during flowering periods, poses a significant risk to honey bees, as residues can contaminate nectar and pollen, which are vital food sources for these pollinators.

To mitigate these adverse effects, the study recommends that farmers and beekeepers adopt more sustainable agricultural practices. This includes avoiding the use of chemical pesticides during flowering periods and considering biological alternatives to reduce toxicity. Furthermore, the research calls for increased awareness and education among agricultural stakeholders regarding the importance of protecting honey bee populations, which are essential for pollination and biodiversity.

Overall, the findings of this study serve as a crucial reminder of the interconnectedness of agricultural practices and environmental health, emphasizing the need for responsible management of herbicides to ensure the survival of honey bees and the ecosystems they support.

References

- Aleksandra, L., Adriana, N., Ireneusz, N., & Anna, G. (2021). Effects of insecticides and microbiological contaminants on *Apis mellifera* health. *Molecules*, 26(16), 50–80. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules26165080>
- Angela, E., Gradish, J., Steen, A., Cynthia, D., Scott-Dupree, G., Christopher, C., ... & Helen, T. (2019). Comparison of pesticide exposure in honey bees and bumble bees: Implications for risk assessments. *Environmental Entomology*, 48(1), 12–21. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ee/nvy167>
- Batra, S. W. T. (1995). Bees and pollination in our changing environment. *Apidologie*, 26(5), 361–370. <https://doi.org/10.1051/apido:19950501>
- Blacquiere, T., Smagghe, G., Van Gestel, C. A., & Mommaerts, V. (2012). Neonicotinoids in bees: A review on concentrations, side-effects and risk assessment. *Ecotoxicology*, 21(4), 973–992. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10646-012-0863-x>
- Dauda, A. M., Nasiru, A., & Suleiman, M. (2019). The impact of some agricultural practices on population status of honey bee, *Apis mellifera* L., in Katsina State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Entomology Research*. ISSN: 2455-4758.
- Johanna, B., Marion, L., & Marie-Pierre, C. (2017). The exposure of honey bees (*Apis mellifera*; Hymenoptera: Apidae) to pesticides: Room for improvement in research. *Science of the Total Environment*, 587–588, 423–438. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.02.062>
- Kaya, M. Y., Gültekin, Y. S., & Gültekin, P. (2023). Evaluation of honey bees within the scope of sustainable development goals and ecosystem services. *Düzce Üniversitesi Bilim ve Teknoloji Dergisi*, 11(5), 2397–2408. <https://doi.org/10.29130/dubited.1383016>
- Kessler, S. C., Tiedecken, E. J., Simcock, K. L., Derveau, S., Mitchell, J., Softley, S., ... & Wright, G. A. (2015). Bees prefer foods containing neonicotinoid pesticides. *Nature*, 521, 74–76. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature14414>
- Marcelo, A., Aizen, L. A., Garibaldi, S. A., & Cunningham, A. M. (2008). Long-term global trends in crop yield and production reveal no current pollination shortage but increasing pollinator dependency. *Current Biology*, 18(20), 1572–1575. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2008.08.066>
- Moffat, C., Buckland, S. T., Samson, A. J., McArthur, R., Pino, V. C., & Bolland, K. A. (2016). Neonicotinoids target distinct nicotinic acetylcholine receptors and neurons, leading to differential risks to bumblebees. *Scientific Reports*, 6, 24764. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep24764>
- Mohamed, E. I., Hoda, M. N., & Entsar, I. R. (2015). Toxicity and biochemical changes in the honey bee *Apis mellifera* exposed to four insecticides under laboratory conditions. *Apidologie*, 46, 177–193. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13592-014-0312-y>
- Mustafa, M. O., Adeoye, O. T., Abdulalzeez, F. I., & Akinyemi, O. D. (2015). Mitigating effects of climate change and deforestation on bees with respect to their ecology and biology. *Journal of Environment and Ecology*, 6(2), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.5296/jee.v6i2.7960>
- Nnamonu, L. A., & Onekutu, A. (2015). Green pesticides in Nigeria: An overview. *Journal of Biology, Agriculture and Healthcare*, 5(9), 48–62.
- Oluwaseun, T. O. (2009). Economics of honey production in Ijebu Division of Ogun State (Unpublished M.Sc. thesis). Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ogun State, Nigeria.
- Stoner, K. A. (2016). Current pesticide risk assessment protocols do not adequately address differences between honey bees (*Apis mellifera*) and bumble bees (*Bombus* spp.). *Frontiers in Environmental Science*, 4, 79. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2016.00079>

Straub, L., Williams, G. R., Pettis, J., Fries, I., & Neumann, P. (2015). Superorganism resilience, eusociality, and susceptibility of ecosystem service-providing insects to stressors. *Current Opinion in Insect Science*, 12, 109–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cois.2015.10.002>

Tijani, B. A., Ala, A. L., Maikasuwa, M. A., & Ganawa, N. (2011). Economic analysis of beekeeping in Chibok Local Government Area of Borno State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 19(2), 186–192.

Tirado, R., Simon, G., & Johnston, P. (2013). Bees in decline: A review of factors that put pollinators and agriculture in Europe at risk.

Greenpeace Research Laboratories Technical Report, 1–48.

Traynor, K. S., Tosi, S., Rennich, K., Steinhauer, N., Forsgren, E., Rose, R., ... & Fahey, R. (2021). Pesticides in honey bee colonies: Establishing a baseline for real-world exposure over seven years in the USA. *Environmental Pollution*, 279, 116566.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.116566>

Yan Ping, C., & Reinhold, S. (2007). Honey bee viruses. *Advances in Virus Research*, 70, 33–80.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-3527\(07\)70002-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-3527(07)70002-9)